

Grant Agreement Number: 824671

SUPER MoRRI – Scientific understanding and provision of an enhanced and robust monitoring system for RRI

D3.3 Super MoRRI Platform and Dashboard

Author(s): Lucian Rusu, Andrei OGREZEANU, Cristina Ivan, George Manea (SIMAVI)

Submission Date: 25.01.2021

Version: 1.0

Type: Demonstrator

Dissemination Level: Public

Project website: www.supermorri.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824671. The opinions expressed in this document reflect only the authors' view and in no way reflect the European Commission's opinions. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Table of Contents

List of Figures	3
List of Tables	4
List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	5
Executive Summary	6
1. INTRODUCTION	7
1.1. Scope and Objectives of the Deliverable	7
2. Platform and Dashboard Architecture and Plan Overview.....	8
2.1. Overall System Architecture	8
2.2. Platform/Website Re-Implementation	9
2.2.1. New Requirements and Justification	9
2.2.2. Technical Implementation	11
2.2.3. Demonstration of functionalities.....	12
2.3. Dashboard α Version Implementation	17
2.3.1. Overview of Requirements	17
2.3.2. Technical Implementation	18
2.3.3. Demonstration of Functionalities	19
3. CONCLUSIONS.....	27

List of Figures

Figure 1: Global Architecture View	8
Figure 2: Initial Wireframe Depiction of Home Page.....	10
Figure 3: Map Functionality based on Google Maps	12
Figure 4: Search Functionality.....	13
Figure 5: Blog Functionality	14
Figure 6: Manage Partners Functionality.....	15
Figure 7: Event Management.....	16
Figure 8: Administration of users and roles: users with various roles can be created.....	19
Figure 9: Dashboard administration: Indicator and Country Administration	20
Figure 10: Dashboard administration: creating and updating indicators and other necessary nomenclatures, parsing CSV files to define data series.....	20
Figure 11: Geo Map representation	21
Figure 12: Bar chart data representation	22
Figure 13: Time-series data representation.....	22
Figure 14: Possibility to select indicators, countries or years for data representations	23
Figure 15: Graphics export functionalities.....	24
Figure 16: Data series export functionalities	25
Figure 17: Display metadata associated with indicators	26
Figure 18: Storing data series in Content Repository	26

List of Tables

Table 1: List of Indicators Presented in the Dashboard Alpha Version	17
--	----

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CMS	Content Management System
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DB	Database
DoA	Description of Action
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
JPEG	Joint Photographic Experts Group (image compression format)
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
PDF	Portable Document Format
PHP	PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
RDBMS	Relational Database Management System
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SVG	Scalable Vector Graphics
WP	Work Package
XLSX	Office Open XML

Executive Summary

This deliverable type is that of a “Demonstrator.” It accompanies the Super MoRRI Platform and development of the Dashboard Release under Task 3.4.

The Super MoRRI Platform/Website can be found at: <https://super-morri.eu/> (hosted by Fraunhofer ISI). This Platform is fully functional and in use by the Super MoRRI Project and available to the general public on the Internet. In the second half of 2020, the technical backbone of the Website was replaced in order to achieve higher levels of usability and provide more functionalities.

The Super MoRRI Dashboard is currently an early release alpha version (per DoA). It is available at: <http://195.82.130.213/dashboard> (hosted by SIMAVI). An alpha version is “an early version of a program or application, typically unstable, but useful to show what the product will do. Sometimes this stage is referred to as a preview version. Sometimes no more features are added after this release, but bug fixes continue. This release comes after a pre-alpha version and before a beta version. As opposed to a beta version an alpha version is usually not feature complete.”¹ This version contains an important feature graphically displaying data series with countries as units of analysis. However, further features will be added based on new data series and further inputs from the Super MoRRI Consortium. This version is aimed at the Super MoRRI Consortium Members including European Commission Services.

This Document presents these two components and their main functionalities. For a full exploration of their functionalities, the reader is invited to visit them at the web addresses indicated.

¹ Wictionary The Free Dictionary. https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/alpha_version, Accessed December 3rd 2020.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Scope and Objectives of the Deliverable

This deliverable type is that of a “Demonstrator.” It accompanies the Super MoRRI Platform and the development of the Dashboard Release under Task 3.4.

The Super MoRRI Platform/Website can be found at: <https://super-morri.eu/> (hosted by Fraunhofer ISI). This Platform is fully functional and in use by the Super MoRRI Project and available to the general public on the Internet.

The Super MoRRI Dashboard is an early release alpha version (per DoA). It is available at: <http://195.82.130.213/dashboard> (hosted by SIMAVI). An alpha version is “an early version of a program or application, typically unstable, but useful to show what the product will do. Sometimes this stage is referred to as a preview version. Sometimes no more features are added after this release, but bug fixes continue. This release comes after a pre-alpha version and before a beta version. As opposed to a beta version an alpha version is usually not feature complete.”² This version contains an important feature set graphically displaying data series with countries as units of analysis. However, further features will be added based on new data series and further inputs from the Super MoRRI Consortium. This version is aimed at the Super MoRRI Consortium Members including European Commission Services.

This Document presents these two components and their main functionalities. For a full exploration of their functionalities, the reader is invited to visit them at the web addresses indicated.

² Wictionary The Free Dictionary. https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/alpha_version, Accessed December 3rd 2020.

2. Platform and Dashboard Architecture and Plan Overview

2.1. Overall System Architecture

The overall Super MoRRI System architecture is a three component architecture comprising:

- The Website/Collaborative Platform;
- The Dashboard and Visualization Component;
- The Self-Assessment Tool.

See Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Global Architecture View

This document reports on the first two components as the implementation of the third, the Self-Assessment tool, is dealt with in WP6.

2.2. Platform/Website Re-Implementation

2.2.1. New Requirements and Justification

The initial Super MoRRI Website/Platform was developed with the need to have a Website in place as soon as possible. Hence, the technology choice was guided by availability, since the website host (Fraunhofer ISI) had already access to licences for the Weblication Content Management System (<https://www.weblication.de>). By M3 of the project a fully functional Website was put in place.

However, at the initiative of the University of Leiden Team (ULEI), in their role as lead of WP7, it was noted that the initial website and its base technology had many limitations which made the Website difficult to operate:

“Being an unpopular CMS, Weblication ends up limited to base components, lacks documentation in multiple languages (the documents available are mostly in German), and does not count with advanced functionality available in most leading CMS, such as:

1. Custom content sections for:
 - a. News;
 - b. Events;
 - c. Blog;
2. Automated download libraries;
3. Striking photo galleries;
4. Adequate integration with social media;

Considering the analysis of what Weblication has to offer, the Leiden team suggests a review of alternatives to improve the Super MoRRI website.”³

Therefore, a collaboration between ULEI and SIMAVI begun to overhaul the Super MoRRI Website/Platform. The new technology chosen for the Website was WordPress (the currently most popular CMS solution). ULEI and SIMAVI collaborated closely in defining the requirements, choosing the graphical theme, placement of diverse elements on pages, etc.

An initial wireframe depiction of the Home Page was generated as shown in Figure 2 below:

³ ULEI, Internally circulated document, 2020.

← → ↻ ↑ <https://www.super-morri.eu/super-morri/index.php> Title

[About](#)
[News](#)
[Blog](#)
[Events](#)
[Twitter](#)
[Findings](#)
[Documents](#)

About This Project

Short description of project here. One phase description preferably.

For a fuller overview and details about the project click [here](#)

About Our Network

Short description of network here. One phase description preferably.

For a fuller overview and details about the project click [here](#)

Latest blog posts

Blog post title 1
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

News piece title 2
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
[More...](#)

Findings

???

Twitter Feed

News piece title 1
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

News piece title 2
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
[More...](#)

Upcoming Events

Latest Project News

News piece title 1
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

News piece title 2
Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.
[More...](#)

Contact us:
contact@super-morri.eu

Funding

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No.

Site Info:
Editorial notes
Disclaimer
Privacy Policy
© 2019 Super Morri, all rights reserved

Figure 2: Initial Wireframe Depiction of Home Page

2.2.2. Technical Implementation

WordPress is the most popular website builder in the world. It is highly flexible and easy to customize. Many of the largest companies in the world are using WordPress to manage their sites. WordPress can be managed without any coding or programming knowledge.

At first, we created a test server with Ubuntu 18.04 operating system and additional software needed such as MariaDB for the database, Apache 2 for the webserver and PHP 7 for the website execution. After we prepared the testing server we installed Wordpress5.5 and we added a new purchased theme which provides the new design and functionalities. Also, we installed and configured additional plugins which provide extra functionalities such as file management, contact forms, twitter feeds etc. After the theme installation, we configured every functionality and we applied the necessary design changes. Once the website was ready, we migrated the content from the old website into the new one and we moved the entire new website on the public server by replacing the old one.

2.2.3. Demonstration of functionalities

Among the possibilities enabled by the new system is a map functionality which allows the to change the look and feel e.g., of a Google Map, to add multiple checkpoints, to handle zooming and map centering.

Figure 3: Map Functionality based on Google Maps

The File Management System which allows the content manager to store and manage files like Word documents, PDFs, Excel files etc. was added as well. Files can now be displayed on a page using a list of predefined templates and functionalities like preview, download, sorting or searching.

THE PROJECT ▾ ABOUT US ▾ OUR NETWORK ▾ OUR POSTS ▾ ACTIONS ▾ CONTACT US

Over the development of the Super MoRRI project you will be able to find some of our findings and deliverables in this page.

>> Findings Download all

Title	Description	Size	Date added	Download	
D.1.2	Strategic Development Plan – This is one of the three strategic documents guiding the SUPER MoRRI project, alongside the Implementation Plan (D2.1) and the Case Research Plan (D5.1).	0.95 MB	Oct-2020	Download	Preview
	Case Study co-creation methodology report – This report highlights the development of the selection of the first			Download	

Figure 4: Search Functionality

An enhanced Blog functionality - Wordpress offers a great blog component, after all it was originally designed to be a blog platform – was integrated as well. With extra plugins we improve the base functionality with resources such as: Yoast SEO – a Plugin that can optimize keywords, synonyms and images so that the blog posts (and other content) can perform better in search engine results (SEO). The plugin also analyzes the readability of the post and calculates the Flesch Reading Ease score.

- THE PROJECT ▾
- ABOUT US ▾
- OUR NETWORK ▾
- OUR POSTS ▾
- ACTIONS ▾
- CONTACT US

RRI monitoring beyond Europe: SUPER MoRRI International Satellite Partners

How is SUPER MoRRI going beyond Europe to reflect and

What are SUPER MoRRI Country Correspondents and who are they?

Get to know a bit about the SUPER MoRRI's Country

Latest News

- The NewHORIZon Societal Readiness Thinking Tool**
November 3, 2019
- The RRI ecosystem has officially launched!**
October 3, 2019
- Call for 23 country-correspondents**
September 15, 2019
- Call for stakeholder comments on**

Figure 5: Blog Functionality

Also, the functionality Manage Partners was added. The new website now offers the possibility to create complex partner pages with map features, social media features, members features etc.

Partner Details

LOCATION
Aarhus

ADDRESS
Strøbeløkke Alle 7 8000 Aarhus C Denmark

PHONE
+45 8736 5238

EMAIL
info@dsr.au.dk

WEBSITE
https://dsr.au.dk

NETWORK
[Icon]

Partner Map

Strøbeløkke Alle 7
View larger map

Our Members

Astrid Lykke Birkving

Massimo Graae Losinno

Figure 6: Manage Partners Functionality

Super MoRRI organises numerous internal and external events, such as consortium meetings and the annual events. Registration, programmes, and other resources are included on the website by using theme functionalities like calendar, events search and filter etc.

THE PROJECT ▾ ABOUT US ▾ OUR NETWORK ▾ OUR POSTS ▾ ACTIONS ▾ CONTACT US

ALL ANNUAL EVENTS WORKSHOPS

Figure 7: Event Management

2.3. Dashboard α Version Implementation

2.3.1. Overview of Requirements

The Dashboard and Visualization Component serves to graphically display data and indicators defined, collected and curated in WP2. This Alpha Version of the Dashboard presents a set of 20 indicators. This selected data was primarily provided to SIMAVI by the WP2 Team (AU), and in part further processed by SIMAVI.

Table 1: List of Indicators Presented in the Dashboard Alpha Version

#	Metric/indicator	Source
1	Share of female researchers by sectors of performance, all sectors [rd_p_femres]	Eurostat
2	Share of female researchers by sectors of performance, Business enterprise sector [rd_p_femres]	Eurostat
3	Share of female researchers by sectors of performance, Higher education sector [rd_p_femres]	Eurostat
4	Share of female researchers by sectors of performance, Government sector [rd_p_femres]	Eurostat
5	Glass ceiling index	She figures 2018
6	Dissimilarity index, higher education sector	She Figures 2018, 2012 & 2009
7	Dissimilarity index, Government sector	She Figures 2018, 2012 & 2009
8	Gender pay gap (%) in the economic activity 'Scientific research & development' (NACE Rev. 2, Division 72), 2010 & 2014	She Figures 2018 & 2015
9	Percentage of a country's publications with a sex or gender dimension in their research content	She figures 2018
10	Women to men ratio of inventions, all International Patent Classification (IPC) sections	She figures 2018, 2015 (based on Patstat)
11	Women to men ratio of corresponding authorship in all fields of R&D	She figures 2018, 2015
12	2.1.1.1 Intramural R&D expenditure (GERD) per inhabitant by sectors of performance (all sectors) [rd_e_gerdtot]	Eurostat
13	2.1.1.2 Intramural R&D expenditure (GERD) as a percentage of GDP by sectors of performance (all sectors) [rd_e_gerdtot]	Eurostat
14	2.1.2.1 Patent applications to the EPO by priority year per million inhabitants [pat_ep_ntot]	Eurostat
15	Percentage of publications open access (All)	CWTS Leiden based on WoS and Unpaywall data
16	Percentage of publications open access (Green)	CWTS Leiden based on WoS and Unpaywall data
17	Percentage of publications open access (Gold)	CWTS Leiden based on WoS and Unpaywall data
18	Percentage of publications open access (Bronze)	CWTS Leiden based on WoS and Unpaywall data
19	Percentage of publications open access (Hybrid)	CWTS Leiden based on WoS and Unpaywall data

#	Metric/indicator	Source
20	Percentage of publications industry co-publications	CWTS Leiden based on WoS and Unpaywall data

The following chart types were chosen as best to display the data:

- Geo Map
- Bar chart data
- Time-series data

Comparisons can be made according to the following criteria:

- RRI indicator
- Country
- Year

Graphics export functionalities have been implemented in common formats such as PDF, PNG, JPG, SVG and data series in the following formats: JSON, CSV, HTML, XLSX, PDF.

Data series are stored in the Content repository. Repository Service serve the dashboard with the information needed for graphical representations.

2.3.2. Technical Implementation

In the phase preceding the beginning of the development, a series of technologies were analyzed to offer the possibility to cover the requirements defined in the analysis phase.

This component of the system has been designed and implemented in such a way as to meet the objective that the analyzed data series can be easily updated and the addition of other indicators to be accomplished without an additional development / implementation effort. In this sense, the data series were stored in a Content Repository component in the form of CSV files. These files can be easily overwritten if new data sets are available for an indicator. To add new indicators, the Dashboard Administration component was created. In this administration interface we have the possibility to add new indicators and to define all the specific attributes of an indicator such as source, description, important definitions, and the link to the data series stored in the content repository.

This component has been implemented as a Java web application based on a three-tier architecture using CSS, Java Script for the client-side and Java based technologies on the server side. The three-tier architecture provides many benefits for development environments by modularising the user interface, business logic, and data storage layers.

- The Presentation Tier is the front end layer and it is composed of the user interface. The following technologies were used in this layer: Java Script library (Amcharts for defining graphs), CSS and Web Development Frameworks (Vaadin platform).
- The Application Tier contains the functional business logic which drives an application's core capabilities. This layer will be communicating with the Data Tier for retrieving and persisting information into the database. The following technologies were used in this layer: Spring

framework with Spring Boot, Spring Security, Spring MVC, Spring Repositories (JPA/Hibernate) components, Spring Rest Template in order to easy implement access to API services, Hibernate framework for mapping an object-oriented domain model to a relational database.

- For the Data Tier an open source RDBMS: PostgreSQL was used.

2.3.3. Demonstration of Functionalities

The following Figures provide an overview of the key functionalities and their graphical representations/look and feel of the Dashboard.

Administrative Functionalities

Figure 8: Administration of users and roles: users with various roles can be created

Super MoRRI Dashboard

Figure 9: Dashboad administration: Indicator and Country Administration

Name	Code	Description	Enabled	Extraction date
Share of female researchers by sectors of performance, all sectors	rd_p_femres	The indicator provides an aggregate measure of how the labour market per...	true	2020-01-06
Share of female researchers by sectors of performance, Business enterpris...	rd_p_femres_bu...	The indicator provides an aggregate measure of how the labour market par...	true	2020-01-06
Share of female researchers by sectors of performance, Higher education s...	rd_p_femres_hig...	The indicator provides an aggregate measure of how the labour market per...	true	2020-01-06
Share of female researchers by sectors of performance, Government sector	rd_p_femres_go...	The indicator provides an aggregate measure of how the labour market per...	true	2020-01-06
Percentage of publications open access (Green)	percentage_of_...	The indicator provides an aggregate measure of how the labour market per...	true	2020-09-28
Glass Ceiling Index (GCI)	glass_ceiling_in...	The indicator provides an aggregate measure of how the labour market per... (DOI) that are registered as publish...	true	2019-11-27
Dissimilarity index, higher education sector	dissimilarity_ind...	The indicator provides an aggregate measure of how the labour market per... index comparing the proportion o...	true	2020-01-06
Dissimilarity index, government sector	dissimilarity_ind...	The Dissimilarity Index (DI) indicates the percentage of either women or m...	true	2020-01-06
Gender pay gap (%) in the economic activity 'Scientific research & develop...	gender_pay_gap	The indicator provides a metric of the difference between the average gros...	true	2020-01-06
Percentage of a country's publications with a sex or gender dimension in th...	percentage_of_a...	The indicator shows the proportion of peer-reviewed publications that integ...	true	2020-01-06

Figure 10: Dashboad administration: creating and updating indicators and other necessary nomenclatures, parsing CSV files to define data series

Main Functionalities

Figure 11: Geo Map representation

Figure 12: Bar chart data representation

Figure 13: Time-series data representation

Indicators

Share of female rese ▾

Country

Estonia × Germany ×

Denmark × Czechia ×

Bulgaria × Greece × France ×

Croatia × Italy × ▾

Years

2009 ▾

- 2005
- 2006
- 2007
- 2008
- ✓ 2009
- 2010
- 2011
- 2012
- 2013
- 2014
- 2015

Figure 14: Possibility to select indicators, countries or years for data representations

Figure 15: Graphics export functionalities

Figure 16: Data series export functionalities

3. CONCLUSIONS

This document presented the Super MoRRI Platform and Dashboard implementation under Task 3.4. The Super MoRRI Platform is fully implemented and in use by the Project as a platform for dissemination of project information as well as a collaborative platform with partners. The Dashboard and Visualization component, while quite advanced in terms of being able to display a variety of Project Data, is for now considered an alpha version available to the Consortium members including Commission Services for internal consultation, feedback and testing before becoming publicly available and fully integrated with the Project Website/Platform.

SUPER MoRRI

Scientific Understanding and Provision of an Enhanced and Robust Monitoring system for RRI **Horizon 2020, Science with and for Society Work Programme 2018-2020**, Topic: SwafS-21-2018 **Grant Agreement Number: 824671**

